

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF UZBEKISTAN: PROBLEMS AND OPPORTUNITIES

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Abstract

Today, one of the principles of democracy in the education system of the developed countries of the world is the availability of general educational institutions at all levels for people with disabilities. In world practice, one of the directions for implementing the principle of accessibility to the educational process of persons with disabilities is inclusive education. The article discusses the current situation of inclusive education in higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan, analyzes the successes and achievements in this direction, identifies problems and barriers to the effective implementation of inclusion in higher education, and develops recommendations for the comprehensive and effective development of inclusive education in higher educational institutions.

Keywords: legal framework, higher education institution, infrastructure, digital economy, inclusive education, persons with disabilities, convention, concept, building architecture, infrastructure.

Introduction. In the era of digitalization of the economy, there are trends all over the world to master and introduce new technologies into the educational process based on innovative educational platforms for joint learning in an audience of healthy people and people with certain health problems. This direction in the world educational practice is referred to as inclusive education. Inclusion has entered the practice of the educational process in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The education of children with special needs is one of the main tasks for the country. This is a necessary condition for creating a truly inclusive society, which is directly 4-10 of the 17 goals of sustainable development for humanity in the 3rd millennium, which Uzbekistan also adheres to. Today, our society has set itself the task of comprehensively supporting the rights of people with disabilities (disabled health), to put into practice the opportunity for them to receive a full-fledged education in all parts of this process.

In our opinion, the most acceptable and effective direction for the implementation of this task is precisely inclusive education. Inclusive education is a living organism, a living process, which implies a creative approach to the learning process, both on the part of teachers and parents. After all, every child requires an individual approach, everyone has the right to education and recognition of their abilities in society" [1].

The purpose of the study is to consider the actual situation of the state of affairs in this direction in our republic, as well as to provide possible recommendations for further improvement of the inclusive education system in our country in order to make inclusive education a reality for a large number of children and their families.

Today, more than 700 thousand people with disabilities live in Uzbekistan, of which more than 100 thousand are people under the age of 16 (According to the data of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic). In recent years, at the state level, there have been a number of positive reforms in the field of the regulatory framework aimed at the legislative level to consolidate

the rights and obligations of persons with disabilities in our republic. In particular:

1. In 2020, the Law "On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities" [2] was adopted, which describes the rights and guarantees of people with disabilities for housing, including benefits, education and employment, as well as available infrastructure, information and public services .

2. On June 7, 2021, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev signed the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan №-695 "On Ratification of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities" (New York, December 13, 2006) [3], which provides for: ratifying the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and recognizing that persons with disabilities have legal capacity on an equal basis with others in all aspects of your life. Taking into account this circumstance, take appropriate measures to ensure that persons with disabilities have access to support and replacement decision-making mechanisms, including the limitation of the legal capacity of persons with disabilities, in appropriate circumstances and in accordance with the law.

3. On October 13, 2020, a resolution was adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev No. 4860 "On measures to further improve the system of education and upbringing of children with special educational needs" [4], which provides for the improvement of the regulatory framework for the inclusive education system, to create a mechanism for training, retraining and advanced training of qualified teaching staff for the system inclusive education, as well as to strengthen the material and technical base and provide institutions in which inclusive education has been introduced with special devices (lifting devices, ramps, railings, etc.), necessary literature, teaching aids, equipment and teaching aids for various professions;

4. On October 8, 2019, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev No. UP 5847 "On approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of

Uzbekistan until 2030" [5]. One of the important points of the concept is to expand the coverage of socially vulnerable segments of the population with higher education, in particular persons with disabilities.

Stating, we can say that in recent years, effective work has been done in our republic in the field of protecting the rights of people with disabilities. But, it should be noted that in practice the implementation of laws, as well as adopted by-laws, is not always sufficiently effective. In reality, the adopted laws and by-laws should contribute to the involvement of people with disabilities in all spheres of society, which is an important priority for the new Uzbekistan at the present stage of development.

The implementation of the norms and standards prescribed in the above legal acts is aimed at enabling people with disabilities to take part in the socio-economic life of the country, use the services of the appropriate infrastructure, receive medical services, free access to employment and proper education.

Based on the foregoing, there is a need for a more detailed study of this topic, as well as the relevance of the chosen research topic.

The methodological basis for the study of this work was the legal acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of development of inclusive education, dialectical and statistical methods, analysis of literature and periodicals, as well as a personal-creative approach in the study of topics. The problems and directions of development of inclusive education in higher educational institutions are considered and studied in the works of William Seitz [6, 7], Yusupov D. [8], F. Bakaeva and D. Muratov [9], Alekhin S.V. [10], Akimova O.I. [11], Shipitsyna L.M. [12], Kraineva E.I. [13], Pugachev A.S. [14] Z.J. Adylova [15] and others.

The author, in presenting this work, aims to analyze the current situation in the development of inclusive education in universities in Uzbekistan, identify existing problems, and develop recommendations for improving the implementation of inclusion in universities.

Analysis and results: The practice of inclusive education in educational institutions of Uzbekistan dates back to the era of Soviet times. Then, under the Soviet regime, people with disabilities studied in specialized educational institutions in isolation from their peers. Today, science has gone far ahead, in many scientific and practically tested scientific studies of Western scientists it has been proved that the greatest effect in teaching people with disabilities is achieved when they study together in a group with their peers.

According to UN statistics, 15% of the world's population have disabilities in physical or mental development, and are accordingly registered as persons with disabilities. It should be noted that this indicator tends to increase from year to year, which is largely associated with environmental degradation and disruption of a normal lifestyle, and 80% of all persons with disabilities are in developing countries, and this is directly a warning call for the government of these countries to take urgent measures to adapt this category of persons to a full life in society.

At the end of 2022, the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan reached 36 million people, 60% of whom are young people under the age of 30. According to the statistics of the Republic, officially registered persons with disabilities in the Republic make up 2.1% of the total population of the country. But this indicator can be quite distorted due to the lack of a census of the country's population. Uzbekistan has not conducted a population census since independence in 1991; the first census is scheduled for 2023, however, the State Statistics Committee does not include questions on disability in the census as recommended by the Washington Group on Disability Statistics, citing a lack of funds and expertise in defining disability [16].

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, in order to implement the principle of integration of science, education and science, under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Mirziyoyev Shavkat Miromonovich, a concept for the development of the higher education system until 2030 has been developed. The purpose of this concept is to deepen reforms in the field of higher education, pursuing the training of competitive highly qualified personnel based on advanced foreign experience. In the concept of the development of higher education, special attention is paid to the introduction and development of the foundations of inclusive education. In particular, it is provided:

- increase the types of educational services provided to students with disabilities and improve their quality;
- wide development of inclusive processes in education, introduction of adaptive technologies;
- create additional conditions for students with disabilities in the buildings of student hostels and higher educational institutions;
- take measures to provide educational institutions with the necessary literature and teaching aids for this category of students, material incentives and support for students from population groups in need of social protection.

On December 1, 2017, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically improve the system of state support for persons with disabilities" [17] was issued, according to which a number of benefits were provided for persons with disabilities when entering a university. In particular, from the 2018-2019 academic year, persons with disabilities of groups I and II were provided with an additional 2 percent quota for admission to the national universities of the country. At the same time, the minimum score in the entrance exams was also reduced to 56.7 points (30% of the maximum possible score of 189 points) to allow persons with disabilities to gain access to the higher education system.

However, despite the existing benefits for the admission of persons with disabilities to universities, the percentage of enrollment in higher education for this category of people remains quite low, and this is primarily due to the unpreparedness of most universities in the country to train these people, which manifests itself in the lack of an accessible environment for people with disabilities. , which creates a kind of segregation

and discrimination based on disability in higher education institutions. The lack of an accessible environment for teaching people with disabilities in universities is manifested primarily by:

- The architecture of buildings and the infrastructure of structures adjacent to buildings is not adapted to the training of persons with disabilities;
- Educational buildings of the majority of universities in Uzbekistan are four floors and higher, however, if we consider in the regional context, many of them do not have elevators, and for those who have, the elevator does not work and is subject to appropriate repairs, which in turn creates difficulties when moving through the buildings of persons with disability with deviations in the musculoskeletal system;
- Due to the sharp increase in quotas for admission to the country's universities, most universities are faced with a lack of classroom fund, as a result of which the class schedule has to be ranked and changed in the audience to conduct classes for one group of students in the context of each pair, and this contributes to the training of students of each pair in different classrooms located on different floors. In this case, high stairs and lack of ramps are a serious barrier to entry and movement in the building for people in wheelchairs;
- In many universities of the country, there is a shortage or absence of special educational and educational-methodical literature intended for teaching people with disabilities;
- A very serious problem of higher education in Uzbekistan, in general, inclusive, in particular, is the low provision of educational institutions with highly qualified personnel;
- Places of common use (canteen, library, toilet) of many universities of the country are not adapted to the needs of persons with disabilities, are not equipped with specialized equipment, which makes it difficult for students with disabilities to visit these places;
- Most of the teaching staff of the country's universities do not have special skills in teaching people with disabilities;

Today, for many people with disabilities, university education should not only be about obtaining relevant knowledge, but also about acquiring life and social skills, which the country's universities should be ready to provide.

In this regard, we believe that one of the priority tasks of the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the further development of inclusive education, strengthening the material and technical base of educational institutions, as well as creating all conditions for the full implementation of the principle of rights and codes of persons with disabilities prescribed in the UN Convention "On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities which our republic has already ratified.

It should be noted that a number of positive trends are observed in this direction, the main of which are manifested in the practical actions of the government to deepen reforms aimed at developing inclusive education in the country. In particular: at the expense of the attracted funds of the Asian Development Bank, a project is being implemented to develop inclusive education in the country, projects have been developed and

implemented to strengthen the material and technical base of specialized boarding schools and orphanages "Mehribonlik".[1]

The problem of developing inclusive education and supporting the rights and freedoms of persons with disabilities in the Republic of Uzbekistan is also addressed in the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. In particular, in the 4th priority area "Conducting a fair social policy, developing human capital", the 66th goal "Formation of an effective system of support for persons with disabilities, improving the quality and standard of their life" is directly devoted to the protection and realization of the life rights of persons with disabilities in our country. republic.[18]

On December 3, 2021, on the International Day of Persons with Disabilities, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, noted: "Critically evaluating our work with the most vulnerable category of the population - the disabled, we will continue to mobilize all the forces and opportunities so that they never feel themselves, actively participated in public and economic life"[19] – the President noted, which once again testifies to the close attention of the leadership of Uzbekistan to the protection of the rights and freedoms of persons with disabilities, as well as to the further development and improvement of the inclusive education system in our country.

Based on the foregoing, we consider the policy pursued by the country's leadership in the field of inclusion development in our country as the most demanded and relevant in modern realities, contributing to people with disabilities in our country to lead a full-fledged lifestyle, actively participate in the economic and political life of society, and also fulfill their civic obligations.

Conclusions and offers:

In the current realities of the socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the construction of the education system of the republic, taking into account the implementation of access to education for people with disabilities, is at the stage of its formation and needs comprehensive support from the state. Significant work is underway in Uzbekistan to create living conditions, education for people with disabilities, a legislative framework has been created to create conditions for the further development of people with disabilities, adopted the Concept for the development of inclusive education in the system of public education in 2020–2025, the Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030. In addition, the President of the country approved the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, aimed at creating a socially significant support system for people with disabilities, improving the quality and standard of their life.

Despite the progress made in the formation and implementation of inclusion in higher education in Uzbekistan, a number of problems have been identified related to the inadequate level of training of the teaching staff for an inclusive form of education, the architectural and engineering infrastructure of buildings and structures that do not meet the requirements of persons

with disabilities, as well as the lack of special adapted towards inclusive learning curricula.

In order to develop and effectively implement an inclusive form of education in higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan, in our opinion, it will be acceptable to solve the following tasks:

➤ Improving the legal framework for an inclusive model of education in line with the provisions and principles of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities; harmonization of the system of statistics and data collection related to persons with disabilities, based on generally recognized international definitions and tools;

➤ Construction of new and reconstruction of existing new buildings and structures, taking into account the adaptation of their architectural and planned development to the needs and requirements of persons with disabilities;

➤ Improving the system for the training and advanced training of teaching staff directly involved in the inclusive model of education;

➤ Based on the capabilities of the republic and individual regions, to form a system for monitoring the current state and development trends of inclusive education, with the active participation of social services for the care of persons with disabilities and the implementation of programs for their rehabilitation, training and employment in accordance with international standards and norms;

We believe that the implementation of these recommendations will help achieve the goals envisaged by the Concept for Reforming the Higher Education System until 2030 and implement reforms for the effective integration, adaptation and development of inclusive education in educational institutions.

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